

Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge, H2020

D6.2: Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication of Results

Deliverable information	
WP	WP6, Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation
Document dissemination level	PU Public
Deliverable type	R Document, report
Lead beneficiary	NISV
Contributors	KCL, OU, DP, UniBo
Document status	Final
Document version	V1.0
Date	30/06/2022
Authors	Marloes Bontje (NISV, Task Leader), Roosmarijn de Groot (NISV, Task Leader), Yasemin Bagci (NISV), Jesse de Vos (NISV), Nicole Emmenegger (NISV)

Page Break

INTENTIONALLY BLANK PAGE

Project information

Project Start Date: 1 January 2021

Project Duration: 40 months

Project website: <http://www.polifonia-project.eu>

Project contacts

Project Coordinator

Valentina Presutti

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

Department of Language, Literature and Modern Cultures (LILEC)

E-mail: valentina.presutti@unibo.it

Project Manager

Marta Clementi

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

Research division

E-mail: marta.clementi3@unibo.it

POLIFONIA consortium

No.	Short name	Institution name	Country
1	UNIBO	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA	Italy
2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOORBEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS SRL	Italy

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars and citizens will be able to navigate, explore and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts – or music objects such as tunes, scores, melodies, notations – along with relevant knowledge about them. Areas of focus are:

- links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.),
- cultural and historical contexts,
- opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and
- facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoires, reportages, news, biographies, reviews),
- facts in different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

Polifonia will organise this by using ten pilot use cases as drivers, addressing preservation, management, study, and interaction with musical heritage:

- **Pilot 1 BELLS** aims to provide tools and methods, through which Historical Bells heritage can be better known and put in relation with other parts of cultural heritage.
- **Pilot 2 ORGANS** will extract a knowledge graph out of the text of the Orgelencyclopédie, which will provide digital (and quick) access to such huge and detailed knowledge, including connection to data about aspects of their wider historic contexts.
- **Pilot 3 FACETS** aims to tackle content-based music retrieval by building a faceted search engine (FSE) for large collections of music documents.
- **Pilot 4 INTERLINK** focuses on intergrating digital music libraries. The pilot aims to provide tools and services that facilitate researchers and curators to establish links and, by doing so, enabling a story-telling space across different sources, time and space.
- **Pilot 5 CHILD** builds a knowledge graph of the historical experience of music in childhood, using life writing (letters, diaries, memoirs, travel writing) and other historical texts as sources for adult reflections on music heard in childhood.
- **Pilot 6 TUNES** uses the digital music collections of the Meertens institute to trace possible international origins of Dutch early popular music and interlink the melody collection with a large number of other European collections.
- **Pilot 7 MUSICBO** aims to provide tools and methods through which Bologna heritage can be known and enjoyed by the wide public. A user-friendly and appealing multimodal interface will enable users to navigate music-related collections and thematic multilingual corpora compiled with music texts, texts on

Bolognese musicians, local performances that marked the development of European music, as well as their receptions in Italy and across Europe.

- **Pilot 8 [TONALITIES](#)** develops tools for the modal-tonal identification, exploration and classification of monophonic and polyphonic notated music from the Renaissance to the 20th century.
- **Pilot 9: [ACCESS](#)** will develop new ways to enhance participation and engagement in music: for the general public; for those with hearing impairments; and for those with physical disabilities.
- **Pilot 10 [MEET UPS](#)** focuses on supporting music historians and teachers by providing a Web tool that enables the exploration and visualisation of encounters between people in the musical world in Europe from c.1800 to c.1945, relying on information extracted from public domain books such as biographies, memoirs and travel writing, and open-access databases.

The overall goal of the project is to create an ecosystem of computational methods and tools for heritage knowledge on the Web. These tools support discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Experiments and validations performed in real-world settings are crucial in that regard. These settings are identified by musical heritage stakeholders, both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters. They can be cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive summary

This Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication will serve as a reference point throughout the Polifonia project. As the project advances it will be reviewed every six months to make sure it still addresses the needs of the project and its stakeholders effectively. This document is divided up into seven parts.

Following a general introduction, it outlines the main dissemination goals and structures them into three phases that roughly coincide with the three years of the project. The following chapter describes the various target audiences of Polifonia. Chapter four connects these target audiences to specific outreach activities that have either already taken place or that are planned. The chapter on exploitation describes current ideas about how the Polifonia results can be leveraged after the end of the project. These ideas will evolve over time as project results become available and are shared with various stakeholders.

The impact assessment contains an overview of the various metrics as of M6 and M18 (social media engagement, number of publications and articles, etc.), and compares these metrics with the impact targets of M24 and M36. Finally, the next steps are described for this document and how it will be updated over the course of the project. These updates will also serve as quantitative and qualitative reports on completed and upcoming communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. The current version of this plan provides an overview of the results achieved by month 6 and 18 in relation to the goals stated in the Polifonia proposal.

Document History

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Author(s) -Institution
V0.1	20/05/2021	First draft released	Yasemin Bagci & Jesse de Vos (NISV)
V0.2	15/06/2021	Internal review	Peter van Kranenburg (KNAW), Eliza Papaki (DARIAH)
V0.2	24/06/2021	Second draft with some corrections and updates	Yasemin Bagci & Jesse de Vos (NISV)
V0.3	25/06/2021	Minor editing	UNIBO
V1.0	30/06/2021	Final version submitted to REA	UNIBO
V1.1	20/05/2022	First draft of second version	Marloes Bontje (NISV) & Roosmarijn de Groot (NSIV)
V1.2	10/06/2022	Internal review	Eleanor Smith (Senior Communication Officer CESSDA) + Peter van Kranenburg (KNAW) + Advisory Board Members + Data Management Team
V1.3	24/06/2022	Second draft with some corrections and updates	Marloes Bontje (NISV) & Roosmarijn de Groot (NSIV)
V1.0	27/06/2022	Editing	UNIBO
V1.0	30/06/2022	Final version to be submitted to REA	UNIBO

Table of contents

1. INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 Project Launch	9
1.2 Role of this deliverable in the project	9
Deliverable D6.1 (M6)	9
Deliverable D6.2 (M18)	10
1.3 Approach	10
2. OBJECTIVES	11
2.1 Phase 1: Raising Awareness	12
2.2 Phase 2: Engaging with Communities	14
2.3 Phase 3: Maximising Sustainability and Impact	14
3. TARGET AUDIENCES	15
3.1 Target Groups	15
4. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITY	17
4.1 Online Presence and Communication	17
Online Presence and Communication (M6)	17
Online Presence and Communication (M18)	19
4.2 Mailing list and Newsletter	20
Status (M6)	20
Status (M18)	21
4.3 Stakeholder's Network	21
Status (M6)	21
Status (M18)	21
4.4 Community Networks	22
Status M6	22
Status M18	23
4.5 Information and Demonstration Activities at events	23
4.5.1 Information and demonstration at events (M6)	23
4.5.2 Information and demonstration at events (M18)	24
4.5.3 Identified potential and prospected events (M18-M36)	24

4.5.3 Collaborations (M6)	25
4.5.4 Collaborations (M18)	25
4.6 Publishing in Scientific Conferences and Journals and presence at other scientific events	25
4.6.1 Presence at scientific conferences (M6)	26
4.6.2 Presence at scientific conferences (M18)	26
4.6.3 Presence at other scientific events (M6)	27
4.6.4 Presence at other scientific events (M18)	27
4.6.5 Identified potential and prospected scientific conferences and events (M18-M36)	28
4.6.6 Publications in scientific journals (M6)	28
4.6.7 Publications in scientific journals (M18)	29
4.6.8 Identified potential publication platforms (M18-M36)	29
4.7 Data publication	30
4.7.1 FAIR protocol	31
4.8 Media coverage	32
4.8.1 Traditional media	32
4.8.2 Platforms reaching scientific audience	32
4.8.3 Selected channels for media coverage (M18-M36)	33
5. EXPLOITATION PLANNING	34
Status (M6)	34
Status (M18)	34
6. IMPACT ASSESSMENT	38
7. NEXT STEPS	39
Action points (M6)	39
Action points (M18)	39
APPENDIX 1	40

1. INTRODUCTION

This document provides an overview over the past and planned communication, exploitation and dissemination activities of the Polifonia project. It compares the impact of those activities against the stated goals. If changes to the dissemination activities become necessary, they are also documented here. In this framework, we first present the high-level goals, second, the target groups, and third, different types of outreach and engagement activities planned for these groups. We conclude by assessing the impact of the activities carried out to date.

The document includes D6.1, prepared six months after the start of the project (M6), and D6.2, prepared eighteen months after the start of the project (M18). Twelve months into the project (M12), "Year 1", was reviewed during the scientific review session on 18 March 2022. The outcomes presented there and feedback received during that session are included and processed in the M18 update.

1.1 Project Launch

The project launch was marked by the release of the project website in January 2021, the first month of the project. It is the main communication tool and source of information about the Polifonia project. Our consortium members share the latest news and updates about the project and its relevant partners on this platform. It is also an important channel for raising awareness and engaging with the wider communities interested in AI and musical heritage. Messages about the project are disseminated via Polifonia's social media accounts.

The Polifonia website contains: the project description, public dissemination material, information on project progress and results, relevant industry news and upcoming events and conferences. Its structure will be expanded in line with the developments and results of the project in the following months.

1.2 Role of this deliverable in the project

Deliverable D6.1 (M6)

The outcomes of Deliverable D6.1 are essential for the activities and strategy of the WP6 that focuses on Engagement, Dissemination and Exploitation Planning. Input and requirements for the Polifonia website have been compiled in the first deliverable by Digital Paths¹.

The version of May 2021 was the first detailed dissemination plan prepared in WP6 that included the target groups, dissemination plans and the tools used to reach them and impact indicators to assess these activities. With regular impact assessments we will evaluate the various dissemination activities and adjust if needed in the following versions of this deliverable. By aligning with the exploitation plan, the project will ensure a sustainable outcome and continue to exist in other forms.

¹ Our tenth consortium partner is Digital Paths. This digital agency has developed Polifonia's brand identity and helps Polifonia to create a strong network and to spread all the news that involve the project. They have set up a communication plan and social media strategy.

Deliverable D6.2 (M18)

The version of May 2022 serves on the one hand as a report of achieved results and tracking of dissemination activities and on the other hand as an exploitation plan. The updated version includes reflections on the target groups, dissemination plans and the tools used to reach them. There are also impact indicators to assess these activities. This deliverable also contains a strategy for the completion of the exploitation plan. In this version we evaluate the strategy outlined in D6.1 and adjust the strategy as needed.

1.3 Approach

For this deliverable, we looked extensively at plans of other European research projects, as well as at the resources made available by the H2020 programme on the Dissemination and Exploitation of research (e.g. Ioannis SAGIAS, 2019). We asked the project partners and members of the advisory board to provide us with details on channels for communication and examples of specific communities with which they already engage about the project results. We were also interested in which communities they see as potential users of the results of Polifonia.

2. OBJECTIVES

The goal of Polifonia is to build a digital ecosystem for European Musical Heritage interlinking music objects with relevant knowledge about their cultural and historical context, expressed in different languages and styles, and across centuries. The ecosystem will include methods, tools, guidelines, experiences, and creative designs, openly shared according to the FAIR data principles.²

The aim is to provoke a paradigm shift in musical heritage preservation, management, studying, interaction and exploitation. The objective of the dissemination activities is to support this goal and increase the visibility of the project among multiple target groups.

The Dissemination Plan identifies and analyses the information needs of the potential stakeholders. These refer to their level of interest in the project and their influence on the outcome, as well as their preferences for communication and engagement channels. The critical impact factor for this is that we can share up-to-date research results and project outputs accurately and promptly without the risk of breaching confidentiality.

We have identified four major dissemination objectives. These will help us to reach the different target groups and make decisions on the instruments that we will use in order to disseminate the project's results and communicate with third parties.

The four main objectives are:

- I. **Raising awareness about the project's vision and goals** by establishing the necessary communication channels for the different target groups. For example, scholars can be reached by participation in scientific conferences. Social media accounts are used to reach the general public. Industry stakeholders can be reached via individual networking and public presentations at industry events. Art festivals and events can be used to reach culture professionals and enthusiasts.
- II. **Reaching out to academics, music heritage professionals and other future industry adopters** in order to communicate Polifonia results and achievements. Additional communication channels can be established to communicate with IT professionals, programmers, heritage institutions and music (heritage) consumers and to gather valuable feedback.
- III. **Fostering technology uptake** by bringing the Polifonia technologies to the attention of other developers of solutions for the heritage and music sector. Documentation and manuals for all tools and technologies available within the Polifonia Ecosystem will be provided.
- IV. **Promoting scientific and technological achievements** by ensuring that the outcomes of Polifonia are published in leading journals and presented at the leading conferences in the respective domains. Innovation and the advancement of the state of the art in various disciplines and topics will be highlighted such as AI in humanities, digital musicology and linked open data among others.

We divide the project's dissemination activities into three phases that roughly coincide with the three years of the project.

² The F.A.I.R. principles: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

2.1 Phase 1: Raising Awareness

In the first phase of the dissemination activities, we want to raise awareness and gain a reputation as a promising Horizon 2020 project that will advance the state of the art and generate innovative and highly relevant results.

Our main tools for this are the website (see section: Online Presence and Communication), social media channels such as Twitter and LinkedIn (see Figure 1) and open source communities such as Github (see 4.4 Community Networks).

We have set a communication strategy that is reflected in the Editorial Calendar and Writing Guidelines (see Annex 1). We build interest by publishing relevant information on these channels, linking to both our own results as well as external content of interest to our targeted communities. To engage with our communities, we make sure to diversify the social media posts by including photos or tweets, and news on music heritage with a broader appeal. We also share our project news and updates on our website. In this way, we aim to capture people's imagination of what the future music heritage could be like. We can also highlight our claim that Polifonia will play a major role in shaping new avenues for music heritage.

Figure 1: Polifonia social media channels: Twitter, LinkedIn. (captured in June 2022)

On top of the digital dissemination activities we also raise awareness through events for academia, industry and the general public (see Figure 2). Digital Paths has produced dissemination material that is available to all partners (See Figure 3). In addition, Digital Paths has created support material for the individual dissemination efforts of all partners. This includes a professionally designed logo (see Figure 4) in various mutations as well as deliverable and slide templates.

News from polifonia

Figure 2: News section on the Polifonia website (captured in June 2022)

Press Area

Press contacts: press@polifonia-project.eu
Download **Press Kit** [here](#)

Figure 3: Press area on Polifonia's website (captured in June 2022)

Figure 4: Polifonia logo in different versions

2.2 Phase 2: Engaging with Communities

After having focused on identifying relevant communities, informing and generating interest in the work of Polifonia in phase 1, phase 2 primarily focuses on engaging with the identified communities. The purpose here is to position Polifonia as **“playing the soundtrack of European history”** in the future of music heritage. Making stakeholders look forward to the tangible results that Polifonia is going to deliver is another aim.

In the second year, we will release the first results of Polifonia that stakeholders and target audiences will be able to interact with. Building on the position and the interest we fostered in the first phase should make it easier for us to have the relevant communities use our first results and provide us with actionable feedback. This second phase will see the initially one-way flow of information, from Polifonia to the various communities, become a co-creation process with discussion and feedback rounds. This will empower Polifonia to include the stakeholder feedback into upcoming pilot iterations and software releases, thereby improving the project’s output. In section 3 ‘Target Audiences’, we enlisted the communities relevant for the Polifonia project. Section 4 shows the tools and engagement activities we plan to start a dialogue with the various communities.

2.3 Phase 3: Maximising Sustainability and Impact

The last phase of the dissemination activities will build on the project’s reputation and the active community of invested stakeholders. In this stage, Polifonia will offer products: completed software prototypes, a Web portal and interactive tools, a digital artistic installation, and ten real-world use cases. These products will be ready for reuse by developers and scholars. Using these tangible products and results we will focus on convincing all stakeholders that the complete music heritage field will profit from the Polifonia music heritage ecosystem. Convincing academic stakeholders and developers will lay the foundation for a successful exploitation of project results.

3. TARGET AUDIENCES

We have identified five main types of audiences for the Polifonia project: 1) scientific, 2) heritage, 3) industry, 4) general public and 5) education.

The table gives an overview of the different target groups within each of these categories. Our communication and dissemination activities are geared towards these communities. The following chapter details our strategy to gain visibility and engage with them.

3.1 Target Groups

The communication activities are geared towards the following target groups:

Scientific	i) Humanities and social science scientific communities. Scholars working in the fields of Music Heritage, (Music) History, Media Studies, Theatre, etc. These scholars are looking for improved data and tools to facilitate their work in finding patterns and connections.
	ii) Information Sciences. Scholars working in the fields of Artificial Intelligence, Semantic Web, music interfaces, Music Information Retrieval, Sound and Music Computing, Open and Linked Data and Knowledge Graphs. These scholars are interested in new research and technologies for the emerging fields of music encoding, multi-sensory data, cultural AI, and many other areas where Polifonia will create an innovative portal and tools.
Heritage	i) Heritage institutions and providers of musical heritage resources who are interested in tools that facilitate their work. They have an interest in increasing large-scale interoperability between heterogeneous musical heritage resources and in reducing the effort required for integrating music heritage resources.
	ii) Libraries and maintainers of musical catalogues who are interested in tools that facilitate the management of large collections through automated music classification.
	iii) Policymakers concerned with music heritage, who can use the outcomes of Polifonia to set the agenda for the collection and distribution of musical heritage.
Industry	i) Music producers and artists who reuse digital musical heritage to produce new forms of art and novel participatory experiences.
	ii) Programmers (early adopters) active in the above-mentioned areas, in both non-commercial and commercial sectors (e.g., start-ups).
	iii) Cultural & Creative industries keen to reuse digital data in their activities to engage with and explore music heritage, as well as to create new business models based on these technologies (e.g., new avenues for tourism and festivals).

General public	i) The general public. People who are interested in music history and who engage with content (and ads) which are more relevant to them.
	ii) People with hearing disabilities who consume music heritage through different sensory experiences such as haptic devices.
Education	i) Students and teachers who are interested in and involved with the GirlsCodeItBetter ³ initiative, bringing high school female students closer to STEM curricula.

³ The Italian GirlsCodeItBetter initiative (girlscodetbetter.it) aims to bring females closer to IT & STEM by forming a digital design and creation club for girls.

4. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITY

In M6 we have selected six types of dissemination instruments based on the needs of the outlined target groups. Namely: our online presence through website and social media, a mailing list and newsletter, a stakeholders' network, community forums, demonstrations at events, presentations at scientific events and publications in scientific journals. In M18 we will add two new dissemination instruments: data set publication and media coverage.

4.1 Online Presence and Communication

Main target Groups: scientific communities, industry, heritage professionals, education and the general public

Online Presence and Communication (M6)

The image shows a screenshot of the Polifonia website and a Twitter feed. The website news includes:

- #Release: Polifonia releases first version of the Polifonia Ecosystem** (30 May 2022). The text states: "The outcomes of the first year of the Polifonia project have been collected in one environment. Researchers, musicians, heritage professionals and anyone interested in musical cultural heritage can now use this ecosystem to find relevant datasets, tools and services in one central spot. Let's find out more." It also mentions: "The Polifonia Ecosystem is a collection of components for developing intelligent applications leveraging..."
- International Semantic Web Conference invites Polifonia to organise workshop** (23 May 2022). The text states: "Valentina Presutti, Michel Buffa, Luc Steels, Jean-François Trubert and Enrico Daga are preparing a workshop on musical heritage and knowledge graphs for the International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC)." It also mentions: "Valentina Presutti, Michel Buffa, Luc Steels, Jean-François Trubert and Enrico Daga are preparing a..."

The Twitter feed shows:

- A tweet from **PolifoniaH2020** (@PolifoniaH2020) dated 13 Jun: "Congratulations to our @albertmeronyo from @KingsCollegeLon for winning the best paper award at Text2KG." It has 10 likes.
- A retweet from **Valentina Presutti** (@vpresutti) dated 30 May, linking to a tweet from **Fiorela Ciroku** (@ciroku_fiorela) dated 30 May: "Ready to present at MK2022! #mk2022 #modularknowledge #eswc2022 #ontologytesting #XDTesting".

Figure 5: Example of news published weekly on Polifonia's website (captured in June 2022)

The project has launched a public [Website](https://polifonia-project.eu/)⁴ and has been present on multiple social media channels since M2, including [Twitter](https://twitter.com/polifoniah2020)⁵ and [LinkedIn](https://www.linkedin.com/company/polifonia-h2020)⁶. The structure of the website was described in detail earlier in this Deliverable as well as in Deliverable D6.1. The goal is to make it easy for each target group to identify and explore relevant

⁴ <https://polifonia-project.eu/>

⁵ <https://twitter.com/polifoniah2020>

⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/polifonia-h2020>

material. While the news section has broad appeal, the publication section will be more focused on scholars and developers.

To maximise the value of the site for different types of visitors (thereby motivating them to return) while at the same time increasing the site's search engine optimisation (SEO) score, we produce original content on selected topics. The writing and formatting guidelines for Polifonia's communication channels are outlined in an Editorial Guidelines document which was distributed and shared among all the partners in M4 of the project (see Appendix 1). This reference document offers a solid structure and ensures that the content created by the ten project partners remains consistent in style and tone of voice.

An Editorial Calendar is maintained and regularly updated with stories and suggested writing assignments per partner to ensure content flow. To engage with their specific target audience, each partner is expected to produce content on a topic of their choosing at least once a month (e.g., current work, highlight of their collection). To this end, we identified various types of content in different lengths and have created bespoke templates for each (i.e., website news, interviews, articles, etc). In addition to these expertise related texts, we ask each partner to write a general introduction presenting their institutions, what they are bringing to the Polifonia project, what they hope to learn from it, and their relation to music.

We combine the contents assigned to each partner with project updates and other relevant news from the field. When possible, posts are synchronised with international days such as International Archives' Day or International Make Music Day. We also make sure to highlight relevant local news by means of translating them into English, thereby making local news and communication accessible on our international platform. For example, events organised by our partners are shared on the Polifonia website. By highlighting local news and events and assigning content to each consortium member, we aim to increase synergies with our partner institutions as well as to expand our audiences. Thus, the Editorial Calendar serves as a source document where all communication activities are consolidated. The regular streams of information shared by the consortium members are made visible to communication officers as well as scholars. It is accessible to all members of the Polifonia project and activities can be planned months ahead.

The project publishes different types of content via the website at least once a week. All the above makes sure that the project's progress is visible to all target audiences.

By June 2021, the project website contained the project description and timeline, press communication kit, news and information on ongoing activities and events. In the future, it presents achieved results, success stories from the (ten) pilots and provides access to the Polifonia Web portal. Its structure may be expanded to contain a repository of documentation such as guidelines, training material, and tools as well as video tutorials. These tutorials will explain how the tools and technologies produced by the project can be used, while taking into account the specific needs of the different target groups.

Online Presence and Communication (M18)

Figure 6: Screenshot of the Polifonia YouTube channel (captured in May 2022).

In M18, the project website will remain the regular go-to place to read about the project in detail and to find out about dissemination and information sharing activities. These can be seminars, publications and slides. The website is also the first platform where we share news, which will be disseminated from there through social channels, the newsletter and the mailing list. It was intended that the news section would be updated weekly, but this pace proves to be a challenge. An allocated news generation system was established at the beginning of the project, but in practice the pilots are not yet able to devote themselves to the set Editorial Calendar and this news delivery. It is simply too early for many pilots to go public with news. We assume that the content flow will improve, but that this depends on the progress of the pilots. It means, however, that we are temporarily unable to follow part of the original communication plan.

Our Twitter and LinkedIn pages are continuously used to post reminders of webinars, YouTube uploads and announcements for participation in (scientific) events. As for these channels, some developments until M18 include:

- The social media department of Polifonia expanded: as of January 2022 Polifonia has a [YouTube channel](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC...) ‘Polifonia Playing the soundtrack of our history’⁷. In June 2022 this channel contained 7 videos, including the expert interviews series and the recordings of our seminar series.
- The description in Polifonia's social media accounts is now adjusted into “EU H2020 Project applying AI for enhancing our understanding of EU musical heritage from the 1500s to the 1950s.” adding the timeframe of our corpus. This timeframe is added in order to find the right audience, fans, and professionals of Early

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/hashtag/polifoniah2020>

music as of 1500 (Renaissance and Baroque), Classical music (1750-1800), Romantic (1800s) and Modern music up to 1950.

- We have been scaling up the accounts that we follow on Twitter in line with our KPIs. This is done to draw attention to the project, but this practice appears to be particularly useful to ‘scout’ and connect with future platforms and organisations that could be interested in our outputs and in future collaborations.
- Our visuals have been improved. A simplified version of visual treatment has been added in order to slightly customise the images used on social media channels and on the website without making them redundant.

4.2 Mailing list and Newsletter

Main target groups: scholars, programmers, heritage and library professionals, companies concerned with music heritage, and (creative) industries.

Status (M6)

An electronic newsletter is issued on a monthly basis. It includes a selection of the month’s best Polifonia project news and updates. The first issue was sent out in M2 (February 2021), since then it has been sent monthly. The newsletter is sent out to individuals and institutions that are subscribed to it.

We are targeting:

- scientific communities and other research projects ;
- programmers and their technology partners, including those that participate in the stakeholders’ network;
- other organisations or companies that can benefit from the Polifonia methods and tools;
- heritage and library professionals, policymakers in cultural heritage;
- public groups or individuals interested in music heritage.

In addition, the newsletter will be posted on the following channels:

- Polifonia website;
- Community forum on LinkedIn (closed group);
- [The DARIAH Artificial Intelligence and Music working group](#);
- Social media channels.

The sign-up form is prominently displayed on the website to motivate people to subscribe. When sending out a new issue of the newsletter, we also promote it via social media channels and the yet-to-be established LinkedIn closed group. This makes it easier for members of that group to share the newsletter with their wider networks. In addition to Polifonia’s own channels, the project partners are encouraged to promote the Polifonia newsletter on their own (social media) channels.

Status (M18)

As of May 2022, 15 newsletters have been issued. During this period there has been some improvement in the layout (fix of the presentation of pilots, switching to the presentation of two pilots per month, and presentation of two main news items and two other news items). In addition, two new sections were added: one presenting the upcoming seminars/presentations or those held in the last month and links to specific pages on the Polifonia website (Seminars and Dissemination). Subscribers receive links to the last video(s) published on YouTube.

4.3 Stakeholder's Network

Main target Groups: scientific communities, (creative) industry, heritage professionals.

Status (M6)

In the first stage, Polifonia's innovation drive will be fuelled by a dedicated Innovation Task Force. This task force will coordinate networking activities to foster the early creation of a stakeholder community. The aims of the task force are to produce effective and easy-to-use solutions for stakeholders outside the project consortium, and to support the external development of products and services that reuse these solutions. The stakeholders' forum will comprise experts within the consortium as well as external organisations (including policymaking bodies), representing professionals from the three specific fields: technical, heritage, and creative.

As a follow-up to the networking activities within the Innovation Task Force, three stakeholder engagement workshops will be organised. One in Amsterdam (month 17), one in Paris (month 25) and one in Bologna (month 36). Before the first workshop, a call will be extended to early adopters. Based on the response, ten early adopters will be selected to form the core of the stakeholders' network. The core group of the stakeholders' network will play a crucial role in providing recommendations and feedback on the development of Polifonia tools. The group will possibly participate in one (or more) WP1 pilots, bringing new requirements and perspectives. Group members will attend the workshops and follow project activities, so that they can provide informed feedback throughout the project. The workshops will be open to other stakeholders, which will be reached through networking and dissemination activities.

Status (M18)

The first stakeholder engagement workshop could not be celebrated in Amsterdam (M17) due to the ongoing Covid-19 world pandemic. It will now take place in Paris in September 2022. Thirtytwo prestigious organisations relevant to European cultural musical heritage and technology in industry, academia and government have been invited to take part. These include the Bibliotheque Nationale de France (BNF), Europeana, DARIAH, Biblioteca Universitaria di Bologna, Idagio, Discogs, and many other relevant parties.⁸ The workshop will take place on one full day, as a satellite meeting of the annual Polifonia project plenary meeting. We will split the day into two parts, where the

⁸ The full list of selected stakeholders includes: Nationaal Instituut voor de Orgelkunst (NiVO), Soprintendenza Archeologica Bologna, Soprintendenza Archeologica Genova, Bibliotheque Nationale de France (BNF), CLARIN, DARIAH, CLARIAH, Europeana, Biblioteca Universitaria di Bologna, The Stables Theatre/Milton Keynes, Officina Futuro Fondazione MAI, SHAPTE, Orgelpark, Stichting Omroep Muziek Bladmuziekcatalogus, Mapping Digitised Newspapers Metadata, Oceanic Exchanges, Discogs, The Internet of Musical Events, Podiumkunst.net, Idagio, Laura Farré Rozada, Chordify, SongFacts, WhoSampled, Queen Mary University of London, Peachnote GmbH, Muziekweb, Utrecht University, MTF Labs, Instituto Complutense de Ciencias Musicales (ICCMU), Rutgers DH initiative, VAST - Values Across Space and Time, Congruence Engine.

first part will revolve around ‘input’ – needs, requirements and feedback from stakeholders towards the Polifonia ecosystem – while the second will do so around ‘output’ – dissemination, a tutorial, and technological adoption activities to nurture the stakeholders as the first generation of early adopters.

4.4 Community Networks

Main target groups: scholars, developers, heritage and library professionals and the general public.

Community forums will be established to present and discuss the Polifonia development process and results with interested developers, as well as public and private organisations.

Status M6

- A community forum will be established on LinkedIn as a closed group, which will make it easier for people outside the project to join. In this way we hope to start an engaging conversation about music and musical heritage.
- Established in May 2021, the [Polifonia H2020 GitHub](https://github.com/polifonia-project)⁹ also functions as a community forum for the technological community. Developers, data scientists, and other interested parties use the GitHub platform to share codes, ask questions and share knowledge. This allows other users to reuse these for their own purposes. These users are not necessarily limited to the institutions or countries that are participating in this project.

Figure 7. The Polifonia H2020 open source community on GitHub

⁹ <https://github.com/polifonia-project>

Status M18

- The [GitHub community](#) has been active since May 2021 and has 43 members (including four outside the collaborators) and 54 repositories.¹⁰
- In september 2021, a [Zenodo community](#)¹¹ was created for Polifonia's output. The collection of the Polifonia community on Zenodo holds eleven entries and includes diverse outputs of the project. These are datasets, applications, academic publications and presentations, all made available in various formats.
- Polifonia joined the [Heritage Research Hub](#)¹² in April 2022. The Heritage Research Hub is a free platform for the cultural heritage research community, allowing users to create and share various types of content. The Hub was created and is managed by the Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage (JPI CH).
- Consortium members have found Twitter to be very useful to reach the project's audiences, possibly more so than LinkedIn. Consortium members and individual members reach their networks through their own accounts, where they receive feedback and engagement. Polifonia recognises this existing infrastructure while distributing its message. The LinkedIn group is therefore not established, since Twitter, but also our GitHub and Zenodo communities seem sufficient to serve the scientific audience.

4.5 Information and Demonstration Activities at events

Main target groups: (creative) industries and the general public.

To communicate the results of Polifonia, consortium members will regularly participate in regional, national and international information and demonstration, on- and offline events. These events address our various target audiences, however, these events will mostly be leveraged to engage with the creative industries and, with and through them with the general public.

We are seeking to establish partnerships with creators with an interest in using novel technologies that will use the outcomes of Polifonia to create installations, performances, interactive applications, etc. to inspire people with our combined European heritage.

By doing so, these events will present key components, methodological advances and music heritage-based solutions to a broader audience in an accessible and inspiring way. A few events have been identified in which further collaboration will be developed. Some events will be hosted directly by Polifonia, such as an online seminars series. The Polifonia Seminar Series includes six seminars in six months with experts in AI, musicology, and related fields. The Polifonia series started in February 2022 and each seminar includes two presentations of 20 minutes, followed by a discussion and Q&A session of 30 minutes.

4.5.1 Information and demonstration at events (M6)

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the consortium was not able to attend any events focusing on sharing information and demonstration until month 6. As the project continues there will be results to display. We will

¹⁰ <https://github.com/polifonia-project>

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/polifonia/>

¹² <https://www.heritageresearch-hub.eu/project/polifonia/>

add to a list of new promising outlets to present project results and increase the overall visibility of the project. However, from January to June 2021, several events were pre-selected as potentially valuable platforms to showcase our project's results, including [AI & Music Festival](#) by [S+T+ARTS](#) and [Sónar](#) (October 2021, Spain), [European Researchers' Night](#) (2021, Europe) and [IDFA DocLab](#) (November 2021, The Netherlands).

4.5.2 Information and demonstration at events (M18)

- [AI & Music Festival by S+T+ARTS & Sonár, 27-28 October 2021, Barcelona \(Spain\)](#). Polifonia presented its first demo research at this festival which is focused on the application of and challenges surrounding the use of Artificial Intelligence in musical creation. The demo was presented on the Hall Stage (and streamed live) by project lead Professor Valentina Presutti.

4.5.3 Identified potential and prospected events (M18-M36)

Pre-selected as potentially valuable platforms to showcase our project's results:

- [Festival Oude Muziek \(2023/2024, The Netherlands\)](#)
The Utrecht Early Music Festival is the largest festival of its kind in the world. For ten days at the end of August, Utrecht city centre becomes the hub of the international early music sector. Since its first edition in 1982, the Utrecht Early Music Festival has presented repertoire from the Middle Ages, Renaissance and Baroque, in more than 250 concerts and other events per edition, to an annual audience that has grown exponentially to more than 70,000 festival visitors.
- [Linecheck: Milan Music Week \(2022, Italy\)](#)
Linecheck is a music festival and meeting point for industry professionals, held in the Italian city of Milan. Forming part of the wider Milano Music Week, Linecheck presents an extensive program of talks, showcases, discussions that explore Italy's music industry and its relationship with the global scene, featuring international players and the major protagonists of Italian industry.
- [Primavera Pro \(2023, Spain\)](#)
Primavera Pro has become the ideal setting for the analysis of what is going on and what is in store for the future of the music world, thanks to its position as a strategic point of cultural exchange between Europe, North America and the Latin American countries. In its more recent editions, over 3000 accredited professionals (half of whom were international) attended and participated in around 100 activities and 59 showcases.
- [Eurosonic \(2023, The Netherlands\)](#)
Eurosonic Noorderslag (ESNS) is a non-profit, European artist only, 100% showcase festival and music conference. By day an international music conference takes place in the conference centre, De Oosterpoort, with 150 panels, keynotes, interviews, workshops, dinners, pitches, parties, presentations and meetings on the latest developments in the European and international music, media, production and interactive industry.
- [AI & Music Festival by S+T+ARTS and Sónar \(2022/2023, Spain\)](#)
The AI and Music S+T+ARTS Festival will bring together a host of creatives, engineers, and scientists in order to explore and demonstrate the creative potential of this technology through a varied program of

live shows, and specially commissioned remote performances, talks, debates and hackathons. Co-organised by Sónar, the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya and béteve, the festival takes place under the S+T+ARTS program of the European Commission, dedicated to linking technology and artistic practice.

- **[Most Wanted: Music \(2022/2023, Germany\)](#)**

Most Wanted: Music (MW:M) is the most important music business conference in Berlin and a rising European hotspot event for music and creative industry professionals worldwide. It is run by the Berlin Music Commission, the music industry network of Berlin. Offering a wide range of inspiring keynotes, interviews and debates, hands-on workshops and matchmaking events, MW:M covers the most current and relevant questions of today's music, tech and creative industries in order to bring direct value to creators and music businesses.

- **[Galway Early Music Festival \(2023/2024, Ireland\)](#)**

Based in the medieval City of Galway, the Galway Early Music Festival features medieval, renaissance and baroque music and dance. The festival also includes talks, demonstrations, exhibition and GEM's Early Music for Young Musicians workshops and concert.

4.5.3 Collaborations (M6)

A few events have already been identified in which further collaborations will be developed until the end of the project in April 2024. As part of the enhanced accessibility and inclusion strategies, Polifonia will collaborate in organising engagement and outreach activities for people with hearing disabilities related to the ACCESS pilot project in WP1. Female high school students will be targeted through the [GirlsCodeItBetter](#) project, to increase their interest in STEM curricula. Performing artists at various festivals will be encouraged to use Polifonia results to creatively engage with Europe's musical heritage. Such collaborations are crucial to demonstrate and make visible the technologies developed by the project and its results. To achieve these ambitions Polifonia is planning to collaborate with the following events:

- [Milton Keynes International Festival](#) by The Stables (2021, United Kingdom)
- [GirlsCodeItBetter](#) (GCIB) events supported by the [Officina Futuro Fondazione](#) (2021, in Amsterdam/Paris/Bologna)
- [Robot Festival \(2021\)](#) the digital art and electronic music festival (Bologna, Italy)

4.5.4 Collaborations (M18)

- Polifonia's [ACCESS pilot](#) led by Simon Holland and [The Stables](#) were selected for funding in the open call 'Co-Creating a New and Different Future for Arts / Higher Education Collaboration'. The participatory project takes the form of workshops organised in the spring of 2022.

4.6 Publishing in Scientific Conferences and Journals and presence at other scientific events

Main target groups: scientific communities, heritage professionals, industry professionals.

The research and technology partners publish the results of their work in leading scientific conferences, events and

journals. An overview of participation in scientific events and the publication activities is presented below. We have also made a selection of potentially interesting events and platforms that could showcase our results (see section 4.6.5).

4.6.1 Presence at scientific conferences (M6)

- [Extended Semantic Web Conference](#) (6-10 June 2021, online).
Participation in the Project Networking Session of EU-funded projects.
- [MIRAGE Symposium](#) (8-9 June 2021, online)
The Polifonia Open University team and researchers in the pilots led by them participated in this symposium, which was an attempt to strengthen the dialogue between computer science and musicology, by presenting to musicologists a broad range of research in computational musicology. The symposium also aimed to gather musicologists' particular needs so as to help shape computational musicology research.

4.6.2 Presence at scientific conferences (M18)

- [Music Encoding Conference](#) (19-22 July 2021, Alicante, Spain).
The Polifonia partners presented various papers at this conference, the annual meeting of the [Music Encoding Initiative \(MEI\)](#) community and all who were interested in the digital representation of music. Music encoding is a critical component for computational or digital musicology, digital editions, symbolic music information retrieval, and digital libraries. This event brought together enthusiasts from various music research communities, including technologists, librarians, music scholars, and students and provided an opportunity for learning and engaging with and from each other.
- [The 3rd Conference on Language, Data and Knowledge](#) (1-3 September 2021, Zaragoza, Spain)
The Polifonia team collaborated with [Odeuropa](#) colleagues to organise the First International Workshop on Multisensory Data & Knowledge during this conference. The goal of this workshop was to advance our understanding of how smells and music are represented in texts and structured data. This research has a strong interdisciplinary character. Its potential impact is significant to many application areas including: preservation and valorisation of cultural heritage, data-driven policy making in cultural heritage, urban planning, artistic performances, applications for scholars in musicology and history, applications for museums, innovation in teaching, maintenance and exploitation of large catalogues, archives and libraries.
- [DARIAH Annual event 2021](#) (7-9 September 2021, Online)
The Polifonia portal: a confluence of user stories, research pilots, data management and knowledge graph technology, Conference Paper presentation by Andrea Scharnhorst, Femmy Admiraal, Peter van Kranenburg, Christophe Guillotel-Nothmann, Paul Mulholland.
- [SEMANTiCS conference](#) (6-9 September 2021, Amsterdam, The Netherlands).
Polifonia consortium members were present during this conference. SEMANTiCS is an established knowledge hub where technology professionals, industry experts, researchers and decision makers

can learn about new technologies, innovations and enterprise implementations in the fields of Linked Data and Semantic AI.

4.6.3 Presence at other scientific events (M6)

- [MEI Linked Open Data Interest Group](#) (26 March 2021, online)
Presentation by Dr Philippe Rigaux and Dr. Albert Meroño Peñuela
- [LiSEH Spring School on Linked Data & The Semantic Web](#) (8 April 2021, Graz, Austria).
Keynote by Dr Meroño Peñuela.
- [Information Science Institute, University of Southern California](#) (11 June 2021, Marina del Rey, United States)
Lecture by Dr Albert Meroño Peñuela.

4.6.4 Presence at other scientific events (M18)

Why Mapping Rules are Important for Constructing your KG?

→ David Chaves
(postdoctoral researcher at DTAI and at OEG)

 Polifonia
Series of seminar
June 28th, 6pm CET

Seeing graphs everywhere: a gentle introduction to SPARQL Anything.

→ Enrico Daga
(Research Fellow at The Open University)

Figure 8. Banner and Twitter card for the fourth episode in the Polifonia Seminars Series, 28 June 2022.

- The Polifonia seminar series started February 2022 and each seminar includes two presentations of 20 minutes, followed by a discussion and Q&A session of 30 minutes. The seminar will be hosted by the Polifonia partner University of Bologna, Alma Mater Research Institute for Human-Centred Artificial Intelligence (coordinated by Dr Valentina Presutti) and includes mainly speakers from UniBo. As of May 2022, three seminars were hosted by Polifonia and distributed on our [YouTube channel](#) afterwards.

- **#1 Polifonia Seminar, 8 February 2022.** Speakers: Nicola Di Stefano (Institute of Cognitive Sciences and Technologies – CNR, Italy) on “An interdisciplinary approach to music perception and cognition: merging empirical aesthetics with bioengineering” and Peter van Kranenburg (KNAW, The Netherlands) on “Some Approaches to Model Melodic Similarity”.
- **#2 Polifonia Seminar, March 8 2022.** Speakers: Michel Buffa (University Côte d’Azur, France) on “The WASABI dataset: Cultural, lyrics and audio analysis metadata about 2 million popular commercially released songs” and Dr Albert Meroño Peñuela (King’s College London, UK) on “Music language models: A need for symbolic representations?”.
- **#3 Polifonia Seminar, 3 May 2022.** Speaker: Mila Bertolo (McGill University, Canada) on “Infants relax in response to unfamiliar foreign lullabies”.
- **#4 Polifonia Seminar, 28 June 2022.** Speaker: David Chaves (KU Leuven and Universidad Politécnica de Madrid) on “Why mapping rules are important for constructing your KG” and Enrico Daga (Open University, UK) on “Seeing graphs everywhere: a gentle introduction to SPARQL Anything”.
- Dr Albert Meroño Peñuela delivered a presentation ‘Music Knowledge Graphs: A need for multimodal representations?’ at the yearly away-day of the Semantic Web Group of the [Vrije Universiteit](#) on 17 May 2022 (Egmond aan Zee, The Netherlands). It covered main Polifonia advances such as the SONAR demo, the MIDI Linked Data Cloud, the Modal-Tonal ontology and the ChoCo dataset.
- Dr Valentina Presutti had a keynote lecture at [Copernicus Festival](#) on 22 May 2022 (Kraków, Poland). The science festival provides lectures, discussions, workshops, film screenings and exhibitions focusing on neuroscience, evolutionary biology, physics, law, and philosophy. The event was organised by the Copernicus Center and the Tygodnik Powszechny Foundation.

4.6.5 Identified potential and prospected scientific conferences and events (M18-M36)

Other conferences and scientific events that have potential for the dissemination of Polifonia’s results will be added to the list below as the project advances:

- European Researchers' Night (2022-2023, Europe)
- [International Semantic Web Conference](#) (ISWC) is a series of academic conferences and the premier international forum for the Semantic Web, Linked Data and Knowledge Graph Community. Dr Meroño Peñuela, Dr Daga and Dr Valentina Presutti, Michel Buffa, Luc Steels, and Jean-Francois Trubert will organise a workshop on Musical Heritage Knowledge Graphs in October 2022. *[confirmed]*

4.6.6 Publications in scientific journals (M6)

Several papers have been submitted to journals and are pending review.

- Dr Meroño Peñuela and co-authors (Pasquale Lisena, Raphaël Troncy) submitted a paper to the *Semantic Web Journal (Semantic Web – Interoperability, Usability, Applicability, an IOS Press Journal)*.
- Dr Daga and Dr Meroño-Peñuela and co-authors (Enrico Motta) submitted a paper to the *Semantic Web Journal (Semantic Web – Interoperability, Usability, Applicability, an IOS Press Journal)*.
- Dr Daga, Marilena Daquino, Paul Mulholland and co-authors, submitted an article to the *ACM journal of Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)*.

- Dr Daga, Paul Mulholland, and co-authors (Luigi Asprino, Aldo Gangemi), submitted a paper to the *SEMANTICS (SEM-EU) conference*.
- Dr Daga, Paul Mulholland, and co-authors (Luigi Asprino, Aldo Gangemi), submitted a paper to the *International Semantic Web Conference (resource track)*.

4.6.7 Publications in scientific journals (M18)

Publications in scientific journals are accessible through our Zenodo community.

- Daga, Enrico, Asprino, Luigi, Mulholland, Paul, & Gangemi, Aldo. (2021, June 11). Facade-X: an opinionated approach to SPARQL anything. *SEMANTICS 2021 EU (SEM-EU)*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4927537>
- Daga, Enrico, Meroño-Peñuela, Albert, & Motta, Enrico. (2021). Sequential Linked Data: the State of Affairs. *Semantic Web – Interoperability, Usability, Applicability, an IOS Press Journal*, to appear.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4927864>
- Daga, Enrico, Asprino, Luigi, Damiano, Rossana, Daquino, Marilena, Diaz Agudo, Belen, Gangemi, Aldo, Kuflik, Tsvi, Lieto, Antonio, Marras, Anna Maria, Martinez Pandiani, Delfina, Mulholland, Paul, Peroni, Silvio, Pescarin, Sofia, & Wecker, Alan. (2021). Integrating citizen experiences in cultural heritage archives: requirements, state of the art, and challenges. *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)*, To appear. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5155956>
- Asprino, Luigi, Carriero, Valentina Anita, Colonna, Christian, & Presutti, Valentina. (2021, October 24). OPLaX: annotating ontology design patterns at conceptual and instance level.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6034251>
- Marilena Daquino, Lucia Giagnolini, & Francesca Tomasi. (2021, November 8). ARTchives: a Linked Open Data native catalogue of art historians' archives. *Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL)*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654634>
- Asprino, Luigi, Carriero, Valentina Anita, & Presutti, Valentina. (2021, December 2). Extraction of common conceptual components from multiple ontologies. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3460210.3493542>
- Poltronieri Andrea, & Gangemi Aldo. (2022, February 11). The HaMSE Ontology: Using Semantic Technologies to support Music Representation Interoperability and Musicological Analysis. First International Workshop on Multisensory Data and Knowledge at the 3rd Conference on Language, Data and Knowledge (2021) (MDK), Zaragoza (Spain). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6047780>
- Poltronieri Andrea, & Gangemi Aldo. (2022, February 11). The Music Note Ontology. Workshop on Ontology Design and Patterns 2021 (WOP), Online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6047855>

4.6.8 Identified potential publication platforms (M18-M36)

Several scientific journals have been identified for the publication of results from the Polifonia project. This list is to be expanded as the project advances:

- *Empirical Musicology Review (EMR)*
- *Transactions of the International Society for Music Information Retrieval (TISMIR)*
- *Music & Science*
- *The Journal of Interdisciplinary Music Studies (JIMS)*
- *The Journal of Musicology (JM)*

- *Popular Music History*
- *Semantic Web Journal IOS Press, Interoperability, Usability, Applicability*
- *Journal of Web Semantics Elsevier*
- *Journal of New Music Research*

4.7 Data publication

Polifonia favours the creation of a digital, open source ecosystem for the Musical Heritage community. Data and software created in this project are therefore published on the [Polifonia GitHub](#) and the repository is synchronised with the [Polifonia Zenodo community](#). This ensures that the DOI for each new version of the code/data is applied. Moreover, all the releases are listed in the [Polifonia ecosystem website](#), along with documentation for easy reuse.

Note that data publication was not included in Deliverable D6.1 and that the first measure point is M18 as part of Deliverable D6.2. Listing the data and software produced by the consortium in detail is part of the Data Management Plan (DMP), as well as defining strategies for open access. The list below includes brief descriptions from the Zenodo entries. For more details on how the project manages its data, see D7.1 First Data Management Plan.

Currently, our Zenodo community 23 publicly accessible data- and software sets:

1. Valentina Anita Carriero, Fiorela Ciroku, Jacopo de Berardinis, Delfina Sol Martínez Pandiani, Albert Meroño-Peñuela, Andrea Poltronieri, & Valentina Presutti. (2022). Polifonia Ontology Network, v0.1 (v0.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6259925>
2. marilenadaquino. (2022). polifonia-project/clef: Improved UI (v1.0.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6559445>
3. Helen Barlow, Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Pilots Module (Child) Metadata [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6672093>
4. Peter Van Kranenburg, Rocco Tripodi, Eleonora Marzi, & Arianna Graciotti. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Pilots Module (Organs) Metadata [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6672193>
5. Elena Musumeci, Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Pilots Module (Bells) Metadata (v0.0.2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6672061>
6. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Books Module Metadata - German Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671771>
7. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Books Module Metadata - English Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671756>
8. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Books Module Metadata - Italian Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671795>
9. Rocco Tripodi, Eleonora Marzi, & Arianna Graciotti. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Books Module Metadata - French Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671830>
10. Rocco Tripodi, Eleonora Marzi, & Arianna Graciotti. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Periodicals Module Metadata - English Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671912>

11. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Data - Italian Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671734>
12. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Data - German Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671663>
13. Rocco Tripodi, Eleonora Marzi, & Arianna Graciotti. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Data - Dutch Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671738>
14. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Data - French Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671728>
15. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Data - Spanish Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671673>
16. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Metadata - Italian Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671571>
17. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Metadata - Dutch Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671519>
18. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Metadata - German Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671494>
19. Rocco Tripodi, Eleonora Marzi, & Arianna Graciotti. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Metadata - French Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671560>
20. Rocco Tripodi, Arianna Graciotti, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Metadata - English Language [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671510>
21. Rocco Tripodi. (2022). Polifonia_Corpus_Wikipedia_Annotation_EN (0.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6701774>
22. Arianna Graciotti, Rocco Tripodi, & Eleonora Marzi. (2022). Polifonia Corpus - Encyclopedic Module Metadata - Spanish Language (v0.0.2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6670984>
23. Guillotel-Nothmann, Christophe, Gurrieri, Marco, van Kranenburg, Peter, Musumeci, Elena, Veninata, Chiara, Berardinis, Jacopo de, Fournier-S'niehotta, Raphaël, Marzi, Eleonora, Barlow, Helen, Daga, Enrico, & Holland, Simon. (2022). Polifonia Survey (Version 19062022) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6664200>

4.7.1 FAIR protocol

In the dissemination for all Polifonia output and products, we make sure that their documentation obliges to the 10 Rules of OpenScience and FAIR as discussed in the first project meet up in Bologna (14 October 2021), and drafted in deliverable D7.2. Updated Data Management Plan (upcoming). This in particular concerns the completeness of output, the use of PID's in bibliographic references, the upload of output to Zenodo with the use of the right metadata (according to the metadata template) on PID's for the authors (ORCID) and PID Polifonia grant. This will be further controlled, advised and implemented between WP6 and WP7 (Data Management Plan team).

4.8 Media coverage

Media coverage needs to be taken up in the strategy to ensure that the public becomes familiar with Polifonia and its results. This has not been included in Deliverable 6.1 in detail and the first measure point is M18.

We intend to have coverage in both traditional media for the general public and industry, and in media targeted at a scientific audience. We therefore need a strategy that considers different media such as radio interviews, blogs, digital and print media. A more proactive strategy in the search for press attention is necessary between M18 and M36. With that in mind, potentially interesting platforms for news dissemination are selected as of M18 and listed in 4.8.3. Selected channels for media coverage & potential media events (M18-M36).

4.8.1 Traditional media

Main target groups: general public and industry.

Here is a list of available media coverage from M1 up to M18:

Channel	Content	Date	Language
Smart City by Radio 24	Polifonia: tutte le dimensioni della musica . Radio interview.	11/2021	Italian
Historisch Café Amsterdam	Peter van Kranenburg over Polifonia: De soundtrack van onze geschiedenis . Podcast.	06/2021	Dutch
AgCult	Dalle Chiese ai palassi pubblici : al via indagine Icccd-Icbsa sul suono delle campane in Italia . Written interview.	05/2021	Italian

4.8.2 Platforms reaching scientific audience

Main target groups: scientific, heritage, education

Here is a list of available media coverage from M1 up to M18:

Channel	Content	Date	Language
Podiumkunst.net	Polifonia - Een boeiend H2020 project dat middels AI het Europees Muzikaal Erfgoed traceert . Online news article.	12/2021	Dutch
Insight SFI Research Centre for Data Analytics	Insight Culture: Polifonia – playing the soundtrack of our history . Blog.	04/2022	English
Meertens Instituut	De soundtrack van onze geschiedenis: onderzoeksproject Polifonia duikt in het muzikale erfgoed van Europa . Press release.	01/2021	Dutch

4.8.3 Selected channels for media coverage (M18-M36)

The following media outlets are intended to be used or contacted:

Channel	Envisoned content	Language
NTR Radio 4 (The Netherlands)	Radio item/interview	Dutch
orgelnieuws.nl (The Netherlands)	Online article	Dutch
Het Tijdschrift Oude Muziek (The Netherlands)	Print article	Dutch
Nederlands Instituut Beeld en Geluid (The Netherlands)	Blog	English
Data Stories Podcast (Spain)	Podcast item/Interview	English
ARTE: The European Culture Channel (EU)	Television broadcast	German/French
Fire Draw Near (Ireland)	Podcast item/Interview	English
Twenty Thousand Hertz (USA/International)	Podcast item/Interview	English
99% Invisible (USA/international)	Podcast item/Interview	English

5. EXPLOITATION PLANNING

Status (M6)

As indicated in the grant agreement, at the 6th month of the Polifonia project, the PEDR focused on the initial strategy for project dissemination and communication. Therefore, we considered it is too early to present a detailed exploitation plan. A general framework for the exploitation avenues and a preliminary set of activities can be found below.

We identified two exploitation models for the project results:

1. **The commercial exploitation model:** the Innovation Task Force will analyse possible business plans on selected technologies produced by Polifonia that can be commercially attractive and may lead to the creation of a startup. The Innovation Task Force and the engagement activities of the stakeholders' network mentioned in section 4.3 will provide input for this.
2. **The technological exploitation model:** the tasks focusing on Enhanced Inclusion Strategies and the Music Heritage Promotion will provide input for this. As part of the inclusion strategies, Polifonia will experiment the (re)use of its technologies with consumers who are deaf or hearing impaired, female high school students as well as the general public and creative industries. As outputs, haptic devices, training materials, a format for an open-source digital art installation or performance may be delivered along with guidelines. These will provide instructions on how to exploit both data and the toolkit to work with Polifonia technologies related to music history.

Status (M18)

Polifonia set a goal of having the guiding exploitation plan ready by M18. At this point in the project, it was desirable that a stakeholder network meeting had already taken place so that the plan could be formed with the initial input from this group. Due to COVID-19, this meeting did not take place. Therefore the prospected general exploitation framework dating from M6 was reworked and with input from internal reviewers and advisory board members developed into the exploitation plan.

In september 2022, the first stakeholder network meeting will take place. We will use that event to present exploitable components, to receive feedback on all project activities and to enable iterations on the core technologies and ontologies. With the input from this meeting the exploitation plan will be conceptualised in full. Changes at the strategic level are not forecasted, but e.g. more detailed leads to early adopters or events for demonstrations are.

Our communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are geared towards specified communities within broader target audiences, the exploitation strategy model is therefore built along the lines of target audiences. We have identified target users and potential scenarios for reuse for several products developed within the project.

- **Target Audience:** For this project we have identified five main types of audiences for the Polifonia project: 1) scientific, 2) heritage, 3) industry, 4) general public and 5) education.
- **Community:** The communities contain ‘**target users**’ that Polifonia wishes to facilitate or engage.
- **Products:** The exploitable components of Polifonia are the resources and outcomes of the project, such as tools, disclosed information or training material - to be called ‘products’. Tools are thoroughly documented and described in the [Polifonia Ecosystem](#).
- **Dissemination activity:** Dissemination activities are linked to the products. These activities can be all kinds of activities that ensure that the target user becomes familiar or engaged with the exploitable component. Activities may include: demonstration, technology uptake, disclosure (incl publication), engagement (general or educational), communication.
- **Events:** Activities are channeled through events. Some of the activities are part of events organized by ourselves, others by external parties. Events are designed to serve more than one purpose.

Target audience	Community ('target user')	Products	Dissemination activity	Event
Scientific	Humanities and social science scientific communities	Polifonia Ecosystem, SPARQL Anything, CLEF, MusoW, Listening Experience, Database (LED), Ceol Rince na hÉireann, MIDI corpus , RAMOSE, FONN - FOlk N-gram aNalysis, LHARP, MIDI embeddings for music link prediction, ChoCo dataset and Knowledge Graph, Polifonia Lexicon, Polifonia Textual Corpus Population, Polifonia Textual Corpus	demonstration, technology uptake, disclosure, communication	Stakeholder’s Network Meeting, Polifonia Seminar Series, attendance at scientific conferences, publications in journals
	Information and computational Sciences	Polifonia Ecosystem, SPARQL Anything, CLEF, MusoW, Listening Experience, Database (LED), Ceol Rince na hÉireann, MIDI corpus, RAMOSE, FONN - FOlk N-gram aNalysis, MIDI embeddings for music link prediction, ChoCo dataset and Knowledge Graph, LHARP, Polifonia Lexicon, Polifonia Textual Corpus Population, Polifonia Textual Corpus, Polifonia Interaction Design Methodology	demonstration, technology uptake, disclosure, communication	Stakeholder’s Network Meeting, Polifonia Seminar Series, attendance at scientific conferences, publications in journals

Heritage	Heritage institutions and providers of musical heritage resource	Polifonia Ecosystem, SPARQL Anything, CLEF, MusoW, Listening Experience, Database (LED), Ceol Rince na hÉireann, MIDI corpus , RAMOSE, FONN - FOlk N-gram aNalysis, MIDI embeddings for music link prediction, ChoCo dataset and Knowledge Graph, LHARP, Polifonia Interaction Design Methodology	demonstration, technology uptake, disclosure, communication	Stakeholder's Network Meeting, Polifonia Seminar Series, attendance at scientific conferences, publications in journals
	Libraries and maintainers of musical catalogues	Polifonia Ecosystem, SPARQL Anything, CLEF, MusoW, Listening Experience, Database (LED), Ceol Rince na hÉireann, MIDI corpus , RAMOSE, FONN - FOlk N-gram aNalysis, MIDI embeddings for music link prediction, ChoCo dataset and Knowledge Graph, LHARP, Polifonia Lexicon, Polifonia Textual Corpus Population, Polifonia Textual Corpus, Polifonia Interaction Design Methodology	demonstration, technology uptake, disclosure, communication	Stakeholder's Network Meeting, Polifonia Seminar Series, attendance at scientific conferences, publications in journals
	Policymakers		demonstration, disclosure, communication	Stakeholder's Network Meeting, Polifonia Seminar Series, attendance at scientific conferences, publications in journals
Industry	Music producers and artists	Open-source digital art installation in collaboration with artists, MIDI embeddings for music link prediction, ChoCo dataset and Knowledge Graph, Ceol Rince na hÉireann, LHARP,	demonstration, technology uptake, disclosure, communication	Stakeholder's Network Meeting, pitch at Linecheck: Milan Music Week 2022, pitch at Primavera pro 2023, pitch at Eurosonic 2023, pitch at Most Wanted: Music (2022/2023, Germany)
	Programmers	MIDI embeddings for music link prediction, ChoCo dataset and Knowledge Graph, Ceol Rince na hÉireann, LHARP, Polifonia Interaction Design Methodology	demonstration, technology uptake, disclosure, communication	Stakeholder's Network Meeting, pitch at Linecheck: Milan Music Week 2022, pitch at Primavera pro 2023, pitch at Eurosonic 2023, pitch at Most Wanted: Music (2022/2023, Germany)
	Cultural & Creative industries	MIDI embeddings for music link prediction, ChoCo dataset	demonstration, technology	Stakeholder's Network Meeting, pitch at Linecheck:

		and Knowledge Graph, Ceol Rince na hÉireann, LHARP, Polifonia Interaction Design Methodology, Sonar app	uptake, disclosure, communication	Milan Music Week 2022, pitch at Primavera pro 2023, pitch at Eurosonic 2023, pitch at Most Wanted: Music (2022/2023, Germany)
General public	General public	Knowledge Graph, Webportal, Sonar app, open-source digital art installation in collaboration with artists	engagement (general or educational), communication, demonstration	Podcast item/Interview at Data Stories (Spain), item at NTR Radio 4 (Netherlands), lecture/performance at Festival Oude Muziek 2023 (Netherlands), item at ARTE: The European Culture Channel (EU), demo at Sonár Festival 2022, lecture/performance at Galway Early Music Festival (2023/2024, Ireland), Podcast item/Interview at Fire Draw Near, Podcast item/Interview at Twenty Thousand Hertz, Podcast item/Interview 99% Invisible
	People with hearing disabilities	Haptic and gestural tools	engagement (general or educational), demonstration, communication	Workshop at The Stables (UK)
Education	Students and teachers	Training materials for female high school students	engagement (general or educational), demonstration, communication	Girslcodeitbetter events (Italy)

6. IMPACT ASSESSMENT

The following table lists communication, engagement and publication metrics such as social media, number of publications and articles, etc. The columns include the actual measured values as of June 2021, values between brackets represent the impact targets as estimated in the Polifonia proposal, the '-' indicates 'no data available'. Latest known values are added for M18, in June 2022.

Metric	M6	M18	M24	M36
Total pageviews on the project website	4,000	14,475	(5,000)	(10,000)
Project dissemination video views (YouTube channel)	-	221	(500)	(2,500)
Followers on Twitter	160	265	(500)	(1,000)
Followers on LinkedIn	47	89	(50)	(100)
Number of stakeholders in the stakeholder network	-	10	(35)	(70)
Number of information and demonstration activities at industry and cultural events	-	4	(5)	(7)
Number of presentations at scientific events	5	10	(20)	(50)
Number of publications in scientific conferences and journals	0	9	(15)	(25)
Number of subscribers to the newsletter	116	151	(200)	(350)
Average number of attendees in public and societal engagement activities	-	-	(0)	(80)
Number of mentions in the media	1	5	(40)	(60)
Average number of attendees in the webinars	-	-	(50)	(50)
Number of members on Github	-	47	(60)	(90)
Number of repositories on Github	-	54	(75)	(100)
Number of entries on Zenodo	-	11	(25)	(75)

7. NEXT STEPS

Action points (M6)

The main dissemination channels for the project have been set up by M1 and are actively used by the project partners to raise awareness and gain reputation. To achieve the desired dissemination impact, the communication officers from NISV and Digital Paths post content on the project website and social media at least once a week, and monitor activities across all channels. The project website publishes original content written by the consortium members as of M4, this posting schedule will now continue in monthly intervals until the end of the project.

We are comparing our stated goals to the current state in the monthly dissemination meetings, making strategic changes if necessary. All of the consortium partners are present in those dissemination meetings.

Action points (M18)

The weekly publication of content turned out to be too ambitious for the beginning of the project. The consortium partners currently do not really use the website as a conduit for their results as intended, but this is mainly due to the fact that they do not yet have concrete results to share. We expect that the editorial calendar can be followed from M24 onwards. We trust that the pilots know how to find us if they are ready to come out with news, nevertheless, we will stress in our communication with the consortium that WP6 and Digital Paths are ready to help.

Between M18 and M36, a more proactive strategy will be used to gain more press coverage. Potentially interesting news platforms and podcasts were gathered in M18 and they will be 'scouted' in the upcoming months. Also, a more proactive strategy will be adopted in arranging on- and offline demonstrations of Polifonia results at events, especially for events targeting the music industry and programmers. This strategy will be set out at the Stakeholder Meeting in Paris in partnership with advisory members who work in the music industry and with relevant stakeholders.

Once all Polifonia components have been identified, we will work with pilot and work package leaders to identify target audiences, dissemination activities and possible events to present the tools and technologies.

APPENDIX 1

EDITORIAL CALENDAR AND WRITING GUIDELINES

Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge

Editorial Calendar and Writing Guidelines

Polifonia's website is the main platform where our consortium members share the latest news and updates from the project. It's also an important channel for raising awareness and engaging with the wider community interested in AI and musical heritage. To do this we need a regular stream of content for our various target groups. Will you help us create these compelling stories?

The writing and formatting guidelines for Polifonia's communication channels are outlined here. As well as online tools that can help you with your writing.

EDITORIAL CALENDAR

The editorial calendar, with suggested topics and authors, is available via this [spreadsheet](#). We will periodically assign partners to write certain stories and request that you also add topics you'd like to write about.

DEADLINE

Send your draft in a Word or Google document to mbontje@beeldengeluid.nl **one week before** the expected publication date (wednesdays). In this way we will have time to assist you with the final edits.

STONE OF VOICE

Polifonia's key audience is music experts and scholars. However our articles and posts should also be accessible to a wider audience. Therefore, the tone of voice Polifonia uses is engaging, informal and professional. We recommend short sentences, and, if possible, limiting the amount of technical words.

GOOD PRACTICE

If other projects or sites are mentioned in your article, please share the relevant links. Remember to cite sources, if you're including information like statistics, quotes, etc.

EDITORIAL TOOLS

<https://hemingwayapp.com/> (to check readability and vocabulary)

<https://www.thewriter.co.uk/tools/readability> (to check that sentences are not too long)

<https://www.grammarly.com/> ("writing assistant" for help with editing and grammar)

EDITORIAL GUIDELINES

These guidelines will help you shape your content for the type of article or news story you are working on

- Website News
- Interview / Introduction *
- Article
- Calls and Announcements
- Social media posts

WEBSITE NEWS

Text length	200 words
Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Title (max 10 words) • Subtitle (max 30 words) • Image or picture • Content (2-4 paragraphs) • Additional and relevant links to related sources • Twitter and Linked-in tags of people and projects mentioned
Headline, subheading	max 30 words, summary of the article
Image specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high quality Image (max 700kb) • horizontal format • recommended sizes for images max 1430 pixel (width) • Include attribution and license per image • If possible share openly licensed image

*PARTNER INTRODUCTION

In this text we ask Polifonia members to introduce themselves by answering three questions, please see [this separate document to introduce your own institution](#)

Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the relation between your organisation/institution and music? • What do you bring to the Polifonia project? • What do you hope to get out of the Polifonia project?
Text length	200-300 words

Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Title (max 10 words) ● Subtitle (max 30 words) ● Content (3 questions) ● Image or capture ● Additional and relevant links to related sources ● Twitter and Linked-in tags of people and projects mentioned
Headline, subheading	max 30 words, summary of the article
Image specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● high quality image (max 700kb) ● horizontal format ● recommended sizes for images max 1430 pixel (width) ● Include attribution and license per image ● If possible share openly licensed image

INTERVIEWS

Text length	400 words
Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Title (max 10 words) ● Subtitle (max 30 words) ● Content (4-5 questions) ● Image or capture ● Additional and relevant links to related sources ● Twitter and Linked-in tags of people and projects mentioned
Headline, subheading	max 30 words, summary of the article
Image specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● high quality image (max 700kb) ● horizontal format ● recommended sizes for images max 1430 pixel (width) ● Include attribution and license per image ● If possible share openly licensed image

WEBSITE ARTICLE

Text length	500 words
-------------	-----------

Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Title (max 10 words) ● Subtitle (max 30 words) ● Content (at least 3 paragraphs) ● Image or picture ● Additional and relevant links to related sources ● Twitter and Linked-in tags of people and projects mentioned
Headline, subheading	max 30 words, summary of the article
Image specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● high quality image (max 700kb) ● horizontal format ● recommended sizes for images max 1430 pixel (width) ● Include attribution and license per image ● If possible share openly licensed image

CALLS AND ANNOUNCEMENTS

Text length	150/200 words
Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Title (max 10 words) ● Subtitle (max 30 words) ● Content (small paragraph) ● Additional and relevant links to related sources ● Twitter and Linked-in tags of people and projects mentioned
Headline, subheading	max 30 words, summary of the article
Image specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● high quality image (max 700Kb) ● horizontal format ● recommended sizes for images max 1430 pixel (width) ● Include attribution and license per image ● If possible share openly licensed image

SOCIAL MEDIA POSTS (TWITTER & LINKED-IN)

Text length	240 characters
-------------	----------------

Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Content (small paragraph)● Twitter and linkedin tags of people and projects mentioned in the text● Information about the news we have to post
Image specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● high quality Image (max 700Kb)● horizontal format● recommended sizes for images max 1430 pixel (width)